

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART IX. INFLUENCE OF POWDERED WALL-MATERIAL

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Influence on the Joshi effect Δi , in 225 mm Hg. (31°) oxygen in a Siemens' tube, at various applied potentials V in the range 3 to 8 kV (r.m.s.) of 50 cycles frequency, of powdered wall-material (glass) has been studied. The discharge current i , the net effect Δi and the relative effect % Δi , at constant V , are greater with gas only in the ionisation space ('normal' discharge) than with gas + powdered glass ('wall-influenced' discharge). The ratio $i_{H.F.}/i_{L.T.}$ (of the high frequency H. F. to the total low tension L. T. current) in dark, at a fixed V , is greater for 'normal' than for 'wall-influenced' discharge, suggesting a diminution in the latter of the H. F. component of i . This has been confirmed by observations on the aerial current which is mainly H. F. The H. F. region of i constitutes the chief seat of the Δi phenomenon. Observed decrease of Δi therefore follows.

Oscillographic studies of the 'normal' discharge reveals that the current consists of a large number of distinct pulses per half-cycle. These pulses are absent below V_m , the 'threshold potential' and increase in number and height with $V > V_m$. Irradiation produces reduction in pulse heights, leading to Δi . In the 'wall-influenced' discharge, the height of the current pulses is greatly reduced; this reduction is the consequence of termination of electron avalanches on the powdered wall-material in the ionisation space. Further, the intensity of the external light received by the inner electrode and that half of the outer electrode farthest from the light source is low. Hence, the small Δi in 'wall-influenced' discharge, as observed.

The essentially surface origin of the Joshi effect Δi was inferred by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1946, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 26; 1947, Abst. No. 25; *Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 15, 281; 1947, 16, 19) from the pronounced influence, on both the magnitude and sign of Δi , of the nature of the excited surface, and of 'ageing' under discharge. It appeared desirable therefore to study the variation of Δi , at constant applied potential V , with increase in the surface area of the (ozoniser) wall-material. This has now been done with a modified (glass) Siemens' tube in which the ionisation space could be filled with and emptied of powdered glass, the discharge being 'wall-influenced' and 'normal' respectively, in the total unfiltered L. T. current, and in the filtered H. F. and filtered L. F. The effect Δi has also been studied in the aerial current, and with a Du Mont cathode ray oscillograph.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement and (a part of) the circuit are shown in Fig. 1. The discharge vessel, an all-glass Siemens' tube*, was filled with purified oxygen at an optimum pressure, in respect of Δi , of 225 mm. (31°) Hg. It also contained the

*Its dimensions are noted in the next page.

wall-material (glass) in coarsely divided form, and was so designed that it could be used, without disturbing the operative conditions, in two ways : When the powdered

Fig. 1

wall-material was outside the ionisation region ; this is 'normal' discharge (N, Fig. 1). Then, by mere inversion of the discharge tube, the whole of the wall-material could be brought into the ionisation region ; the discharge is now 'wall-influenced' (W, Fig. 1). The H. T. electrode consisted of a 10% solution of sodium chloride contained in the inner tube. A helix of bright copper wire, the distance between two consecutive turns being sufficiently large to permit irradiation of the enclosed gas, on the outer tube constituted the L. T. electrode. The tube was excited over 3 to 8 kV (r. m. s.) of 50 cycles frequency. The L. T. current was observed with a reflection galvanometer G actuated by Cambridge vacuo-junction (s) V. J. (Fig. 1). The source of light consisted of a battery of two 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulbs run at 200 volts, and placed at a distance of 17 cm. from the discharge tube. The effect Δi was observed (Table I) in the total (i.e. unfiltered) L. T. current, and in the filtered H. F. and L. F., the circuits (not shown in Fig. 1) being similar to those employed in Part VII (Mohanty, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 215). The value of the capacitance was $0.0004 \mu F$, and that of the inductance, $250,000 \mu H$. The mode of observation of Δi was similar to that described in Part I (Mohanty and Kamath, *ibid.*, 1948, 25, 405). In Table II

are recorded values, at different V, for i_{HF}/i_{LT} and i_{LF}/i_{LT} , in dark and under irradiation, for the 'normal' and the 'wall-influenced' discharges.

* Dimensions of the Siemens' tube :

External diameter of the outer tube	...	19 mm.
Internal " " "	...	17
External " inner "	...	8
Internal " " "	...	6
Thickness of the glass wall	...	1
Inter-electrode distance	...	4.5
Length of the discharge space	...	22.0 cm.

TABLE I

Potential variation in the L. T. current of Joshi effect in oxygen produced 'normally' and under 'wall-influence'.

pO_2 —225 mm. (31°). Temp.—26°. 50~. Source of light—two 200 watt 200 volt incandescent (glass) bulbs, 17 cm. from the ozoniser.

V (kV. r. m. e.).	'Normal' discharge. (Gas only in the discharge space). Detector—vacuo-junction. Heater 9.11a 40aDubilier across H terminals.			'Wall-influenced' discharge. (Gas+ powdered wall-material in the discharge space). Detector—vacuo-junction. Heater 575 a.		
	L. T.	H. F.	L. F.	L. T.	H. F.	L. F.
	i_D	...	...	...	...	...
	i_L	...	...	...	...	...
3.74	Δi	...	...	...	...	...
	% Δi	...	...	...	...	...
	i_D	11.66	10.63	3.46	3.00	2.00
4.27	i_L	7.35	7.14	2.45	3.00	2.00
	Δi	4.31	3.49	1.01	...	...
	% Δi	37.0	32.8	29.2	...	...
	i_D	14.15	13.04	4.12	3.87 (1.00)	2.83
4.81	i_L	9.38	8.60	2.83	3.74	2.83
	Δi	4.77	4.44	1.29	0.13	...
	% Δi	33.7	34.1	31.3	3.4	...
	i_D	16.49	15.24	5.00	5.2	4.00
5.34	i_L	11.32	10.63	3.61	5.1	3.94
	Δi	5.17	4.61	1.39	0.1	0.06
	% Δi	31.4	30.3	27.8	1.9	1.5
	i_D	18.44	17.35	5.66	6.08 (2.00)	4.47
5.87	i_L	12.88	12.28	4.12	6.00	4.42
	Δi	5.56	5.07	1.54	0.08	0.05
	% Δi	30.2	29.2	27.2	1.3	1.1
	i_D	20.04	18.79	6.33	7.48	5.39
6.41	i_L	14.29	13.64	4.58	7.38	5.34
	Δi	5.75	5.15	1.75	0.10	0.05
	% Δi	28.7	27.4	27.7	1.3	0.9

TABLE I (contd.)

V (kV, r. m. s.)	'Normal' discharge. (Gas only in the discharge space). Detector = vacuo-junction. Heater 9.11A. 40A Dubilier across H terminals.			'Wall-influenced' discharge. (Gas + powdered wall-material in the discharge space). Detector = vacuo-junction. Heater 575A.		
	L. T.	H. F.	L. F.	L. T.	H. F.	L. F.
6.94	i_D	21.23	19.97	6.56	8.83 (2.83)	6.40
	i_L	15.49	14.63	4.8	8.72	6.33
	Δi	5.74	5.34	1.76	0.11	0.07
	% Δi	27.0	26.7	26.8	1.2	1.1
7.48	i_D	21.77	20.76	7.00	10.40	7.35
	i_L	16.15	15.69	5.2	10.30	7.28
	Δi	5.62	5.07	1.8	0.10	0.07
	% Δi	25.8	24.4	25.7	1	1
8.01	i_D	22.27	21.23	7.14	11.79 (3.46)	8.31
	i_L	16.79	16.13	5.39	11.66	8.25
	Δi	5.48	5.10	1.75	0.13	0.06
	% Δi	24.6	24.0	24.5	1.1	0.7

The bracketted figures in 'wall-influenced' are the i_D values obtained with the same vacuo-junction as used in 'normal'.

TABLE II

Proportion of the H. F. and the L. F. in the 'normal' and the 'wall-influenced' L. T. currents in dark and in light.

V (kV, r.m.s.)	'Normal' discharge.				'Wall-influenced' discharge.			
	Dark		Light		Dark		Light	
	i_{HF}/i_{LT}	i_{LF}/i_{LT}	i_{HF}/i_{LT}	i_{LF}/i_{LT}	i_{HF}/i_{LT}	i_{LF}/i_{LT}	i_{HF}/i_{LT}	i_{LF}/i_{LT}
3.74	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.27	0.91	0.30	0.97	0.33	0.71	0.67	0.71	0.67
4.81	0.92	0.29	0.92	0.30	0.73	0.73	0.76	0.76
5.34	0.92	0.30	0.94	0.32	0.77	0.74	0.77	0.75
5.87	0.94	0.31	0.95	0.32	0.74	0.77	0.74	0.77
6.41	0.94	0.32	0.95	0.32	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.74
6.94	0.94	0.31	0.94	0.31	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.73
7.48	0.95	0.32	0.97	0.32	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71
8.01	0.95	0.32	0.96	0.32	0.72	0.70	0.72	0.71

The Joshi effect was also observed in the aerial current. For this purpose, the L. T. electrode of the ozoniser was directly earthed. A moderately sized frame aerial was placed at a distance of 25 cm. from the ozoniser and was earthed through a vacuo-junction. When the ozoniser was excited at $V > V_m$ the 'threshold potential', it functioned as a source of H. F. radiations which were picked up by the aerial. Results for Δi in the aerial current i_{aerial} are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Potential variation of the Joshi effect in oxygen in the aerial current.

$p_{\text{O}_2} = 225$ mm. (31"). Temp. = 26°. 50~. Detector = vacuo-junction. Source of light = two 200 watt 200 volt incandescent (glass) bulbs, 17 cm. from the ozoniser.

V (kV, r.m.s.).	'Normal' discharge				'Wall-influenced' discharge	
	i_D	i_L	Δi	% Δi	i_D	i_L
4.27	8.00	5.00	3.00	37.5	...	...
4.81	10.00	6.56	3.44	34.4	1.41	...
5.34	11.40	7.81	3.59	31.5	...	...
5.87	12.51	8.86	3.65	29.2	1.73	...
6.41	13.46	9.64	3.82	28.4	...	...
6.94	14.39	10.39	4.00	27.8	1.73	...
7.48	15.13	11.09	4.04	26.7	...	...
8.01	15.97	11.79	4.18	26.2	2.00	...

Oscillographic studies of the 'normal' and 'wall-influenced' discharges were made at various V with a Du Mont instrument. Input to this last was obtained from across 15 k Ω in the L. T. of the ozoniser. Fig. 3 contains a typical set of oscillograms for the two modes of discharge, in dark and under light.

DISCUSSION

Examination of data in Table I shows that the system is non-conductive at 3.74 kV. Under 'normal' excitation, *i.e.*, with only the gas in the discharge space, values for the total L. T. current in dark at 4.81, 5.87, 6.94 and 8.01 kV are respectively 14.15, 18.44, 21.23 and 22.27. Under 'wall-influenced' excitation, *i.e.*, with the gas + powdered wall-material (glass) in the discharge space, the current at constant V is markedly diminished. Thus *e.g.*, with the same vacuo-junction as used under 'normal', values for dark i_{LT} at the above values of V, shown in parentheses in Table I, are as low as 1.00, 2.00, 2.83 and 3.46 respectively. This necessitated the use of a more sensitive vacuo-junction for studies of Δi under 'wall-influenced' excitation (*cf.* Table I).

The V— i_{LT} characteristics, in dark and under light, for the 'normal' discharge (Fig. 2) are concave to the V-axis, indicating that the rise in i_{LT} with V, which is rapid near V_m , slows down at higher V. The same behaviour is exhibited by the corresponding characteristic curves for the filtered H. F. and the filtered L. F. Under 'wall-influenced' excitation, on the other hand, V— i curves for the total (unfiltered)

L. T. (Fig. 2), the H. F. and the L. F., in dark and under irradiation, are convex to the V-axis, i.e., the rise in i with V is more pronounced at higher than at low V.

Fig. 2
The Joshi effect in unfiltered L. T. in 'normal' and 'wall-influenced' discharges.

Whilst, similar to the observations of Mohanty and Kamath (*loc. cit.*), and Mohanty (*loc. cit.*; this *Journal*, 1949, 26 553), both the net effect Δi and the relative effect $\% \Delta i$ for the 'normal' discharge vary markedly with V (Fig. 2; cf. Table I) under 'wall-influenced' excitation, the variation of Δi , in the unfiltered L. T. as well as in the filtered H. F. and the filtered L. F., with V is not marked. Further, the lowest V at which Δi occurs in this case is higher than the corresponding potential under 'normal' excitation. Thus, Δi makes its appearance at 4.27 kV under 'normal', whereas under 'wall-influenced' excitation and in the unfiltered L. T., at 4.81 kV,

At constant V , both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ are markedly smaller under 'wall-influenced' than under 'normal' excitation. Thus, under the former, at 5.87 kV, Δi in the unfiltered L. T. is as low as 0.08, whereas under the latter at the same V , 5.56. The corresponding values of $\% \Delta i$ are respectively 1.3 and 30.2. In the filtered H. F. and the filtered L. F., at the above V , values for $\% \Delta i$ are respectively 29.2 and 27.2 under 'normal', and 1.1 and 1.1 under 'wall-influenced' excitation.

It will be evident from data in Table II that under 'wall-influenced' excitation, the proportion of the H. F. in the L. T. current is smaller, at constant V , than under 'normal' excitation. Thus *e. g.*, whereas the ratio i_{HF} / i_{LT} in dark is, at 4.27 kV, 0.91 under 'normal', it is, at the same V , 0.71 under 'wall-influenced' discharge. That it is the high frequencies which suffer reduction in the latter will also be evident from an examination of the magnitude of the aerial current (Table III) which is chiefly H. F. Thus, at 5.87 kV, i_{aerial} in dark for the 'normal' discharge is 12.51 and as low as 1.73 for the 'wall-influenced' discharge. Since Δi occurs preferentially in the H. F. region of i (Joshi, *Nature*, 1944, 154, 147; *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 67; Mohanty, *this Journal*, 1950, 27, 215), reduction of the proportion of the same in the total (unfiltered) L. T. which obtains under 'wall-influenced' excitation would reduce Δi , as observed.

Examination of the structure of the discharge current (Fig. 3) with the cathode ray oscillograph reveals, besides the frequency of the A. C. supply, a remarkably large

Fig 3
Oscillograms of the silent discharge, 'normal' and wall-influenced' at diff. applied potentials
'Normal' discharge.

number of higher frequencies of widely varying strengths (cf. Joshi, *Nature*, 1944, 154, 147; *Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 253; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A22, 389; Deb and Ghosh, *Sci. & Cult.*, 1946-47, 12, 17; 1948, 14, 39; this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 449; Harries and Engel, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, 19, 514). These high frequency pulses are absent at $V < V_m$, and increase in number and amplitude with V increased beyond V_m . *Ceteris paribus*, reduction of the pulse heights leads to Δi^* ; this reduction is proportionately less at higher than at low V .; This is for the 'normal' discharge. Under 'wall-influenced' discharge, on the other hand, the high frequency pulses are almost completely suppressed, and no further diminution in amplitude is perceptible on irradiation. The magnitude of Δi in the 'wall-influenced' discharge is therefore very small.

In the 'wall-influenced' discharge, the number of gas molecules in the applied field is much less than in 'normal', since in the former case most of the volume of the discharge space is occupied by powdered glass. The number of primary electrons is less. Further, electron avalanches starting from the electrodes, and those created within the gas mass, get arrested by the powdered wall-material. The height of the current pulses is consequently less, and Δi smaller, in 'wall-influenced' than in 'normal' discharge, as observed. Moreover, whilst in the 'normal' discharge both the electrodes receive the external light at almost the same intensity, in the 'wall-influenced' discharge the central and the farthest half of the outer electrode get light of much reduced intensity than that half of the outer electrode nearest the lamps. In consequence, the already attenuated current pulses in the 'wall-influenced' discharge suffer no further appreciable suppression on irradiation.

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The total current $i_{L,T}$ flowing through a discharge vessel at a given V ($> V_m$) consists of frequencies ranging from the supply to those in the radio regions, together with a small D. C. due to rectification. The indicator shows the (vector) resultant of the i values due to the various frequencies prevailing at the instant. The H. F. which constitutes a major part of $i_{L,T}$ is the chief seat of the negative effect - Δi (referred to in the text simply as Δi , since it is apparently more familiar), and very high (Shukla, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1949, 53, 1239) and medium (B. B. Prasad, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 29 A, 322) frequencies of the positive effect + Δi , an increase in i_D on irradiation. Oscillographic studies have revealed that depending upon the conditions, + Δi and - Δi co-occur (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1947, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 25). The former is characterised by an increase, under irradiation, in the number or/and the amplitude of the pulses, and the latter by an opposite change; the current indicator shows the balance. Amplitude increase of some of the pulses in the 'normal' discharge is evident from Fig. 3. That - Δi in i_{HF} is not appreciably larger than that in $i_{L,T}$ (Table I) can be traced to the simultaneous occurrence of + Δi .